

Post-custodial Approaches Workshop: in partnership with EMKP

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Happy New Year everyone! As we move into 2025, the year that the OHOS project will wrap up, we are taking a moment to look back at some examples of work conducted during its lifespan. Recently Dr Paulo Loretoa Granados Garcis, Head of the Endangered Material Knowledge Programme based at the British Museum, wrote a short blog summarising their partnership with *Our Heritage, Our Stories*.

You can read this [here](#).

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